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1 Introduction

In this integrative report, we present the methods (traditional and innovative) employed in the LIGHTCAP project and reflect on their efficacy in terms of gaining new insights in light’s effects on human functioning. A lot of the projects are still ongoing, meaning that most often only preliminary conclusions can be drawn at this stage. For further details and referencing we hence would direct the reader to the published and forthcoming manuscripts of individual ESRs. The current deliverable merely serves to sketch the high-level directions of and connections between the numerous studies – performed and ongoing – in LIGHTCAP.

Our consortium was unique in its approach to study non-image forming effects of light (NIF) from different perspectives: architectural, animal and human biological, ecological and neuropsychological. Projects in the LIGHTCAP consortium have used artificial light and daylight as a stimulus to study its effects on mice and humans at different levels, ranging from physiological responses to vigilance, cognition and higher behavioural outcomes (Figure 1). In these efforts, a multitude of new methods (in light dosimetry and light simulation) have been developed and defined, innovative research protocols and measurements have been employed, and under investigated groups have been targeted.

Figure 1: The methods used in LIGHTCAP to study the non-image-forming effects of light.

ANS: autonomic nervous system, OCT: optical coherence tomography, EEG: electroencephalogram, MRI: Magnetic Resonance Imaging, EOG: electrooculogram, TMS: transcranial magnetic stimulation, HR: Heart Rate, HRV: Heart Rate Variability, BT: Body Temperatures (Core and Skin), SC: Skin Conductance, GC: Glucose, MEL: Salivary Melatonin

In the following, we outline the models/protocols/modulators and measures used in LIGHTCAP, with particular emphasis on the links, similarities and complementarities that distinguish the consortium from other projects.

2 Description of methods

2.1 Light as a stimulus

Across the project a wide variety of lighting conditions and light stimuli were used and/or measured. In general, studies can be differentiated by the way in which light was applied, the type of light source(s) used, the range of light levels, the exposure duration, the devices with which the lighting conditions were measured/verified, and the way in which the consistency of the lighting conditions was verified over time. In Table 1, we present an overview of these variables per study in LIGHTCAP.

Light(ing) manipulations are classified based on the targeted light features: spectral, spatial, and temporal distribution of light and its dose or intensity.

2.1.1 Spectral tuning

Several ESRs manipulated the spectral composition of light to target specific sets of photoreceptors (i.e., cones or ipRGCs) Fatemeh Fazlali (ESR05) used the silent substitution method, consisting of using different light spectra that lead to similar ipRGC activation (and for which change between the light conditions are silent) while leading to different stimulation of s-cones, m-cones or l-cones. In contrast, Jose Fermin Balda Aizpurua (ESR03) and Elifnaz Geçer (ESR07) targeted ipRGC activation through the use of metameric lighting to contrast conditions with high vs. low melanopic activation while keeping cone stimulation constant. Roya Sharifpour (ESR04) also manipulated the spectral composition of light to induce differences in melanopic illuminance.

2.1.2 Dosage of light

To gain more insight into the visual and non-visual integration of different light intensities across different methods, several ESRs (ESR02, ESR03, ESR06, ESR07, ESR09, ESR10, ESR11, ESR13, ESR14) have applied light interventions in various steps of intensities. Some of the studies were controlled laboratory studies in which the head position was fixed, others employed a fixed seating position or more free movement. All laboratory studies used LED light sources for the lighting conditions except for one study that used fluorescent sources. Across the studies employing a light manipulation, lighting conditions were predominantly characterized using spectroradiometers calibrated for measuring spectral irradiance, positioned at eye-level in the (typical) viewing direction of the subject. Complementing the laboratory studies, several ESRs (Rafael Lazar (ESR06), Vaida Verhoef (ESR08), Steffen Hartmeyer (ESR13), Megan Danell (ESR14), Myrta Gkaintatzi Masouti (ESR15)) tracked persons' naturalistic light exposure over longer periods of time (days – weeks), through personally worn light meters. In these field studies, intensity, timing and duration were monitored as they vary naturally during participants' daily routine. Moreover, light exposure-derived features were related to outcome measures that were monitored in parallel. In some of these studies highly innovative spectrally resolved dosimeters were used (ESR13, ESR08 - ongoing) and in another study (ESR15) complementary light simulation tools were applied to validate the accuracy of the measurements.

2.1.3 Spatial distribution of light

Qian Huang (ESR01) investigated how vertical patterns in visual scenes alter behavioural states in rodents by studying preferences for one scene over the other in a forced-choice paradigm.

Nikodem Derengowski (ESR12) on the other hand investigated how the spatial distribution of light affects human participants' alertness, cognitive performance, and creativity during early afternoon by manipulating the directionality of light. He tested light coming from different parts of the visual field, thus affecting different locations on the retina, while keeping the vertical illuminance at the eye homogeneous.

Table 1: Overview of studies performed in LIGHTCAP

ESR	Study	Study type	Main outcome	Head position	Control level (mEDI)	Stimulus level (mEDI)	Exposure duration	Light setup	Light Measurement Device
Elif ESR07	1	Lab	EEG	fixed	2.5	55, 175	30 min	LED box, Metameric (fixed Illuminance)	Spectroradiometer
Mahsa ESR05	1	Lab	Melatonin suppression	fixed	8	min-max cone activation (fixed 150 lx mEDI)	2 h	LED panel, metameric (fixed mEDI)	Spectroradiometer
Fermin ESR03	1	Lab	fMRI	fixed	0.2	37, 92, 190	30-70 s intermittent 12-24 min	LED indirect	Illuminance meter + spectrometer
Roya ESR04	1	Lab	fMRI	fixed	0.2	37, 92, 190	30-70 s intermittent 12-24 min	LED indirect	Illuminance meter + spectrometer
	2	Lab	TMS	relatively fixed	25	312, 625	13 min	LED box	Illuminance meter + spectrometer
Nima ESR11	1	Lab	Alertness	not fixed	0	3, 10	1 h	LED ambient	Spectroradiometer, Illuminance meter, Spot luminance (0°,15°,30°)
	2	Lab	Hazard detection	relatively fixed	0.01	0.8, 80	30 min	LED upper FOV	Spectroradiometer, Illuminance meter
Aysheh ESR10	1	Lab	Alertness	not fixed	0	3, 10	1 h	LED ambient	Spectroradiometer, Illuminance meter, Spot luminance (0°,15°,30°)
	2	Lab	Alertness	not fixed	0	3, 10, 99	1 h	LED ambient	Spectroradiometer, Illuminance meter, Spot luminance (0°,15°,30°)
Rafael ESR06	1	Field	Pupil size	not fixed	NA	NA	45 min	Real-world (daytime)	Spectroradiometer (10s epoch)
	2	Lab	Melatonin suppression	not fixed	NA	3, 65, 1300	3 h	Fluorescent ambient	Spectroradiometer, Dosimeter
Vaida ESR08	1	Interview	Daytime complaints	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

ESR	Study	Study type	Main outcome	Head position	Control level (mEDI)	Stimulus level (mEDI)	Exposure duration	Light setup	Light Measurement Device
	2	Field	Sleepiness & fatigue	not fixed	NA	indoor, daylight	6 days	Real-world	Dosimeter
	3	Field	Sleepiness & fatigue	Not fixed	NA	Indoor, daylight	2 weeks	Real-world	Spectrally resolved dosimeter
Ash ESR02	1	Lab (Animal)	Dementia	not fixed	NA	18, 1800	12 h	LED ambient, uniform	Spectroradiometer,
Qian ESR01	1	Lab (Animal)	Behaviour	not fixed	NA	0, 142	20 min	LED ambient	Spectroradiometer, Radiance camera
Richard ESR09	1	Field	Safety perception	not fixed	NA	road lighting uniformity	1 h	Real-world (outdoor night time)	Spectroradiometer Illuminance meter
	2	VR	Alertness, Safety perception	fixed	NA	night vs. day	1 h	VR	NA
	3	Lab	Safety perception	relatively fixed	NA	screen luminance	45 min	Screen	Spectroradiometer Spot luminance meter
	4	Lab	Image luminance need	relatively fixed	NA	screen luminance	45 min	Screen	Spectroradiometer Spot luminance meter
Steffen ESR13	1	Field intervention (dynamic light)	Light exposure	not fixed	100	140, 344	5 days	LED ambient (school), Real-world	Spectroradiometer, Dosimeter
	2	Field intervention (dynamic light)	Light exposure	not fixed	NA	NA	5 days	LED ambient (open plan office), Real-world	Spectroradiometer, Dosimeter
	3	Field	Light exposure	not fixed	NA	NA	1 day	Real-world	Dosimeter, Melanopic radiance camera
	4	Field	Light exposure, Sleep	not fixed	NA	NA	2x 4 days	Real-world (hospital shift work)	Spectroradiometer, Dosimeter
Megan ESR14	1	Field intervention (daylight)	Light exposure	not fixed	NA	0-1500lx	7 days	Real-world	Spectroradiometer, Dosimeter
	2	Field intervention (dynamic light)	Light exposure	not fixed	NA	0-1500lx	7 days	Real-world	Spectroradiometer, Dosimeter
Myrta ESR15	1	Semi-controlled lab	Light exposure	not fixed	NA	0-4000lx	1 day	Simulated one-person office	Spectroradiometer, Dosimeter Simulation Luminance camera
	2	Field (indoor & outdoor)	Light exposure	not fixed	NA	0-4000lx	2 days	Real world, Open plan office	Spectroradiometer, Dosimeter Simulation Luminance camera
Niko ESR12	1	Lab	Alertness	fixed	1 lx	580 lx	46 min	LED box, varying position in FOV and size	Radiance camera Spectroradiometer
	2	Lab	Creativity, alertness	Not fixed	NA	305 lx	120 min	Simulated co-working space	Radiance camera Spectroradiometer

2.2 Response to light

2.2.1 Eye

Within the LIGHTCAP project, we conducted investigations into retinitis pigmentosa in a mouse model and evaluated the pupil size in human subjects.

Retinal measurements

In one fundamental study on a retinitis pigmentosa mouse model, Ashwathi Prithviraj (ESR02) looked into the functionality of melanopsin changes over the course of the degeneration. As part of this study, she employed Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) to capture high-resolution images of the retinas to analyse their structural layers. She measured retinal disease progression with MEA retinal recordings under control and dim red light conditions.

Pupil size

In two studies (ESR05, ESR06), changes in the pupil area were measured by using a silent substitution Pupillograph before and after light exposure. The silent substitution method provides pairs of stimuli that differ only in the excitation of one class of photoreceptors while producing no difference in the excitation of the other photoreceptors. They used a Maxwellian view system with two cameras, which detected both pupils simultaneously. The constriction amplitudes were calculated as the maximum constriction from the average pupil trace, and the ratio of targeted photoreceptors' response amplitude to all photoreceptors' response amplitude is examined. In other studies at the University of Liege (ESR03), pupil size is monitored as a recognized indicator of locus coeruleus activity. The right eye movements and the pupillary size were recorded continuously with an infrared eye-tracking system. The transient pupil response was computed as the change in pupil diameter before and after the auditory tasks under three different light conditions. In a semi-field study (ESR06), the pupil size regulation in dynamic, real-life lighting conditions across the lifespan has been investigated. A wearable infrared video-based eye tracker (Pupil Labs GmbH) has been used for simultaneous sampling of pupil size, and the natural variation in pupil size of healthy participants has been measured across a broad age range under naturally varying light conditions. Last, ESR08 also measured pupil size in the lab (under dim/dark conditions) in a sleep restriction paradigm. Pupil data was recorded during performance tasks.

2.2.2 Brain

In current light research, objective markers are essential to quantify the effects of light on the brain as they can lead to deepening our knowledge in NIF effects of light. For example, it has been reported that cortical excitability follows a circadian oscillation pattern. This probably means that light could have modulatory effects that we could measure with neuroimaging techniques. This is why we use different neuroimaging techniques to comprehensively measure brain activity during different lighting conditions. Animal studies in rodents, particularly mice, also add significant value to the field of research on the effects of light because it allows the use of very controlled experiments where invasive techniques can be used for establishing causalities and mechanisms while keeping a lot of biological similarities with humans. Together, neuroimaging studies in

humans and animal studies using invasive biological techniques enrich our research by providing a more holistic understanding of how light affects several NIF effects.

EEG (ESR04, ESR07)

Electroencephalography (EEG) and Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (TMS) present a practical solution for this purpose. EEG, in particular, offers excellent temporal resolution, enabling us to assess the impact of light on a sub-second scale. EEG, as a technique, measures electrical activity in the brain, capturing voltage fluctuations resulting from neuronal activity. It records various brain wave types associated with different mental states and cognitive functions, with a focus on alpha, beta, theta, delta, and gamma waves. Currently, there are various EEG metrics in use, but results are not always consistent. To address this, we are exploring the potential of EEG to provide useful markers like evoked response potentials (ERPs) time-locked to task responses, their amplitude and phase delays for assessing light's effects. Additionally, we are interested in exploring new measures that might be more sensitive or robust than current markers. For example, we aim to identify the best markers for measuring sleepiness and alertness, recognizing that light can influence these states. We also look for connectivity, EEG microstates, and potentially introspective evoke responses, all with the goal of introducing novel metrics to be able to quantify non-image-forming effects effectively.

EOG (ESR04)

The EOG is measured continuously during one study quantifying alertness levels in teenagers before bedtime in the evening. The number of slow eye movements and the blink rate serve as a proxy of a person's objective marker of alertness/sleepiness level on a rather high temporal resolution.

MRI (ESR03, ESR04)

To enhance our understanding of non-image-forming (NIF) effects of light, we are also employing ultra high resolution (7T) functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI). Specifically, fMRI allows us to assess the blood oxygenation level-dependent (BOLD) activity in subcortical areas related to critical NIF effects, such as working memory, attention, and mood. With the data acquired through fMRI, we conduct a wide range of analyses, with a primary focus on a whole brain analysis providing a comprehensive view of how various brain regions respond to different lighting conditions, a region of interest (ROI) analysis paying particular attention to potential subcortical area like the locus coeruleus, hypothalamus, and thalamus, and functional connectivity analysis to investigate the impact of light on the between-region connectivity in addition to regional activity.

2.2.3 Animal

Animal studies (ESR01, ESR02) also allow researchers to explore the effects of light in several contexts using biological protocols. For example, we are looking for biomarkers related to Alzheimer's in mice, aiming to determine if light exposure could potentially slow down the disease progression (ESR02). This approach not only deepens our knowledge of light's impact on brain function but also holds promise for therapeutic interventions in neurodegenerative conditions like Alzheimer's. We can also record electrophysiological activity in the mice's lateral geniculate nucleus (LGN) in response to different spatial patterned light stimuli (ESR01). This allows us to compare

firing features in neurons of the dorsal and ventral LGN, providing valuable insights into the visual processing of low-frequency spatial patterns. Furthermore, we study the expression of c-fos in the brain after exposure to different light conditions. The expression of c-fos in neurons has provided a useful marker of activated neurons. By analysing this protein expression, we gain a deeper understanding of how light influences neural activity and the associated behavioural responses.

2.2.4 Autonomous nervous system/ endocrine

HR, HRV

Richard Jedon (ESR09) collected HRV measures as an indicator of anxiety. ESR08 also measured ECG data (including HRV) in a sleep restriction protocol by focusing on potential proxies of sleepiness (data to be analysed).

Body temperature

Aysheh Alshdaifat (ESR10) and Nima Hafezparast Moadab (ESR11) collected skin temperature but suggested a different method as it is hard to distinguish from room temperature effects. ESR14 would opt for collecting body temperature as a check measure in future studies. ESR13 collected continuous skin and core body temperature (CBT) from hospital employees working three to four consecutive day- and night-shifts using a relatively novel commercially available wearable sensor attached to the chest, to examine the effects of continuous shift work on CBT rhythms. This sensor estimates core body temperature through the heat flux at skin level and thereby obviates the need for more invasive means of measuring CBT such as a thermal sensor that is swallowed. While these measurements allowed to separate the sample population into participants that exhibited cumulatively earlier and later phase-shifts in their CBT rhythm, the study also showed that this measure of CBT is strongly modulated by (self-selected) sleep and therefore partly constitutes a behavioural measure when collected under real-world settings (i.e., strong masking of the underlying circadian CBT modulation by activity/sleep). ESR08 measured continuous proximal and distal skin temperature (ambient temperature corrected) over 72 hours both in a sleep restricted condition and a normal sleep condition, in order to investigate the effects of sleep pressure on proxies of sleepiness in skin temperature (and DPG) and the rhythmicity of it. The skin temperature data has been monitored in two studies using six surface temperature thermocouples placed on proximal and distal regions of the body surface.

Skin conductance

In one study (ESR09), skin conductance levels have been collected as an indicator of arousal.

Melatonin

In two studies by ESR05, salivary melatonin was collected every 30 minutes 6-7 hours prior to usual bedtime. In one study, the data was collected until 3 hours after participant's bedtime and in the other one two more samples were collected in the next morning. A direct double antibody radioimmunoassay was used for the determination of melatonin levels. The minimum detectable dose of melatonin (analytical sensitivity) was determined to be 0.2 pg/mL, while the functional least detectable dose (limit of quantitation) in the saliva is 0.9 pg/mL. The AUC of melatonin was calculated during the light exposure in each study session.

2.2.5 Behaviour

Subjective

For subjective sleepiness, the Karolinska Sleepiness Scale (KSS) was the most commonly used method across the ESRs (KSS; ESR03, ESR04, ESR05, ESR06, ESR07, ESR08, ESR10, ESR11, ESR12, ESR15). ESR12 recommends using the KSS measurements at several instances across the experiment. Notably, ESR08 used different subjective sleepiness measures and found out that each of them evaluates a different dimension of sleepiness : KSS is more connected to (a lack of) alertness, Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS) to sleep propensity, and Stanford Sleepiness Scale (SSS) to feelings of sleepiness. ESR08 also explored measures of fatigue, the Visual Analog Scale to Evaluate Fatigue Severity (VAS-F) and Patient related outcome measure system for daily fatigue (PROMIS).

Other commonly self-reported items were visual comfort (ESR05, ESR06, ESR07, ESR12, ESR15) and mood/emotional valence (ESR03, ESR04, ESR05, ESR06, ESR07, ESR12). ESR07 noted that adding self-reports of mood or other factors could be beneficial for differentiating between the possible effects on performance. In their study, the focus was on how performance could be affected by ipRGCs stimulated through different light conditions but another explanation might lie through light conditions impacting mood and consequently the performance. Self-reports could be therefore helpful for checking on biases. Myrta Gkaintatzi Masouti (ESR15) employed self-reports for perception of glare and view quality but suggested it would be better to find a way to collect such data without disrupting the participants from their other tasks. ESR09 focused on self-reported arousal (Activation Deactivation Adjective Checklist; ADAACL) and environmental assessment (perceived environmental safety, light appraisal, aesthetic judgements). In their findings, the ADAACL correlated well with rating of perceived environmental safety and seems to be an useful tool instead of the ad hoc safety questions. ESR14 would find self-reports beneficial in their study but could not employ them due to the nature of their study sample (patients with dementia). ESR14 suggested interviewing the caretakers to be able to collect the desired self-reported data at least indirectly. ESR13 used subjective sleep diaries assessing sleep parameters such as sleep times, sleep duration, and sleep quality in all studies. These measures, on the one hand, allow to examine effects of personal light exposure on sleep parameters, but also are crucial meta-data for light-dosimetry studies in general, as they help to contextualize personal light exposure and assess personal light exposure relative to individual sleep periods. In addition to sleep diaries, ESR13 employed an activity diary in one study, where participants indicated daily routines (when they were at home, commuting + mode of transport, at work, at lunch, outdoors or indoors). Similar to sleep parameters, such measures are interesting meta-data for light-dosimetry studies, as they allow to examine how daily light exposures relate to daily routines and environments. Moreover, in light-dosimetry studies performed to validate a lighting intervention (e.g. as part of a post-occupancy evaluation), such insights into daily routines add context to personal light exposure data collected outside of the spaces in which the effects of known lighting conditions are evaluated.

Task performance

Psychomotor Vigilance Task was the most commonly used measure for sustained attention (PVT; ESR03, ESR04, ESR05, ESR06, ESR07, ESR08, ESR10, ESR11, ESR12) although there were some

differences in the specifics. Most often, the 5-minute version was used, but ESR08 also used the 10 min version and ESR11 with ESR10 employed a protocol of 3-minute PVT. The consensus across the ESRs is that ideally they would employ either a longer PVT version (10-20 mins), in more instances across the experiment or with longer inter-stimuli intervals. The reason for these changes is that the PVT would then be, for example, more sensitive to changes in sustained attention (ESR05, ESR06, ESR11), able to observe the ipRGCs activity (ESR07) or to increase the ecological validity (ESR08). The 5 min version was chosen mostly due to practical and feasibility reasons. Both visual and auditory versions were employed across the ESRs, although the auditory variant was preferred to allow for light stimulation via vision. ESR10 would opt for a visual PVT as it is more related to the task of walking and also employing a dual or multiple task approach to increase difficulty.

Other reaction time tasks used were the n-back, always in the 0-back and 2-back variations. Auditory n-back for 24 minutes was employed by ESR03 and ESR04. In ESR11's study they used 10-minute duration with visual (0-back) and auditory (2-back) variants. ESR11 suggests including voice recording of responses during the task, to be better able to assess the performance afterwards. ESR12 used the task (auditory, 5 minutes) and suggested that the 3-back variation might bring stronger results than the 2-back variation used. Oddball Task was used by ESR03, ESR04 (12 minutes) and ESR07 (5 minutes), always auditory. For observing the possible effects of ipRGCs stimulation, ESR07 suggests using a more challenging Oddball (with 2 possible responses) or the n-back task. ESR04 would suggest longer resting periods between the tasks and measuring the brain activity even in the resting periods for more complex picture of the phenomenon at stake and to counter possible carry-over effects during the brain imaging studies. ESR08 and ESR09 used the Attention Network Test (ANT; 20 mins). ESR08 would add a memory task to the ANT or even rather develop a test battery with more complex and real-life related tasks; a mix of tasks for different cognitive components (e.g., decision making or processing speed) to assess more ecologically valid performances. ESR09 also used an auditory two choice test (ATCT; 5 mins) and later Go/No-go (3 mins) to measure reaction times and accuracy as indicators of alertness. The switch to Go/No-go was to be able to also observe inhibition levels as indicators of anxiety. Go/No-go was also used by ESR12 but he suggests making it more challenging, either by decreasing the inter-stimuli interval or by adding more of the no-go stimuli. ESR09 also explored what kind of metrics can be derived from the reaction time task; the speed of responses, proportion of errors and coefficient of variation. These metrics didn't necessarily follow the same patterns across studies implying each of them might carry their specific benefits and fit different purposes.

Other tasks employed include gender-classification task (ESR03, ESR04; emotion manipulation, 18 minutes), hazard detection task (ESR11; visual, 30 minutes), 2 forced choice task (ESR01; preference, 20 minutes) and the three behavioural tests used in ESR02's studies: novel object recognition test, spatial alternation test, spontaneous alternation. ESR02, through her reading and studies, has found that behavioural tests are being conducted under non standardized protocols and this might lead to the different results being reported across studies and the non-reproducibility of published data. Under these circumstances, it might be better to employ other markers for disease progression and pathology. ESR12 also used Mental Rotation Task (3D spatial

rotation, cognition, creativity), Remote Associates Test (RAT; German or English version; cognition, creativity) and Alternate Uses Task (AUT; German or English version; cognition, creativity).

Actigraphy

ESR14 and ESR13 both used actigraphy to measure daily patterns of activity. Actigraphy is a direct proxy of active vs. rest behaviour and allows to estimate periods where subjects were asleep, as well as to derive sleep parameters and estimates of sleep quality (i.e. fragmentation of sleep). Moreover, actigraphy data was used by ESR13 to help contextualize simultaneously collected personal light exposure data, allowing to indicate when subjects were asleep, or when invalid light exposure data was recorded (e.g., when subjects were active but no light was recorded, indicating the device might have been covered by clothing).

Observation methods

ESR02 employed circadian recordings of the home cage activity in the mice studies. ESR13 used activity diaries (see above) to measure daily routines of subjects and when they were inside the evaluated space or not, while ESR14 used personal observations to determine occupant location. They would both lean towards better occupancy tracking in future studies to be able to monitor the daylight exposure and related activities throughout the whole duration of the experiment. ESR15 did occupancy tracking with a logbook (tracking presence on-desk, indoors, outdoors). Face orientation was recorded by a webcam and the videos were analysed (by the software tool OpenFace). In ESR09 measured walking speed as a check measure for arousal levels and indicator of anxiety.

2.2.6 Light as a response/behaviour

While light is an important stimulus affecting human non-visual and visual functions, in the real-world, that stimulus is strongly affected by behaviour, to an extent that personal light exposure in and of itself can be considered a behavioural response. That is, exposure to light is not a passive experience but a behaviour embedded in each individual's location (e.g., photoperiod, local climate), culture (e.g., festivities, norms), and built environment. Consequently, personal light exposure is highly individual, varies across time, cultures and locations and, importantly, is an outcome measure as much as a stimulus for downstream effects on health and wellbeing. Hence, for lighting interventions to be successful, the effects of lighting on behaviour and of behaviour on personal light exposure need to be considered. Similarly, for advancing research on the non-visual effects of light it is crucial that the relationship between light and human responses is studied in real-life settings.

Several ESRs data (ESR06, ESR08, ESR13, ESR14) collected personal light exposure over longer periods of time (days – weeks), through personally worn light meters. While in many cases, personal light exposure was related to other outcome measures or included as a covariate (ESR06, ESR08, ESR13, ESR14), ESR13 and ESR14 also studied light exposure as a response to architectural features (ESR14), lighting interventions (ESR13) and individual daily routines (ESR13). Through spectrally-resolved measurements ESR13 was able to identify not only the quantity of light people were exposed to but also which sources the light came from (e.g. daylight, LEDs, fluorescent light

sources), offering additional insights into the environments that shaped personal light exposure. Taken together, these studies showed that personal light exposure in real-world settings is highly variable within and across individuals, even within the same environments and lighting conditions. Moreover, there often exists a discrepancy between the (designed) lighting conditions in a space to what occupants of that space actually experience, due to their interactions with the environment. ESR15 showed how even individual variations in gaze behaviour can affect how much light a person is exposed to (here: how much light enters the eye over time). These findings reiterate the importance of evaluating lighting design decisions or interventions with light-dosimetry (see also D3.4).

3 Reflection

3.1 Reflections on study design

3.1.1 What/ where is the value of combined methods?

Many of our ESRs combined measurements or methods that are not often combined. For instance, some have combined lab measurements or methods with similar ones in the field (ESR08, ESR15). This may serve to test the ecological validity of findings initially established in simulations or in a laboratory (ESR15), or, to test the validity of ambulatory, uncontrolled field data with more controlled, lengthy or otherwise thorough testing in the laboratory (ESR08). And often of course our researchers also included field measurements to track the light exposure or sleeping patterns prior to lab studies to control for their potential bias on lab findings (ESR08, ESR05). Contrasts between simultaneously collected measures - and their explicit reporting - may help give important insight into pathways of light or even the workings of the human brain in general.

We saw additional novel combinations of measures in studies, for instance, subjective reports of mood during fMRI-centred studies (ESR03), of behavioural measurements and pathology (ESR02), or of the accuracy of light measurements with computer simulation (ESR15). Such broadening of measurements was typically performed for validation purposes or for potential post-hoc statistical control of bias induced by relevant phenomena. The motivation for yet another less common combination (diary of daily routines, ESR13; occupancy tracking with personal light measurements, ESR14) was to render a deeper understanding of the relationship between relevant parameters, in this particular case the architectural/lighting design and actual real-world exposure.

A third type of unusual combinations within our projects pertains to the use of qualitative with quantitative data to help ground the meaning of quite “lean” quantitative measures of mood or mental state in the “rich” lived experiences of participants. A different kind of ‘grounding’ was perhaps seen in EEG studies which combined non-task with task-time measurements (ESR07). Apart from offering longer exposure time, this allows us to also test the light exposure without task effects, as potentially those cognitive or emotional tasks may be alerting or arousing in and of themselves.

3.1.2 Should we collect more or less data?

Of course there is much value in collecting data on more aspects than those one is directly interested in. Throughout the consortium we hear researchers reporting on the importance of collecting not only prior sleep-wake patterns, but also the (extended) light history of participants and DLMO in lab or field-based studies. Thanks to our growing palette of measurements we may begin to detect and understand better important interindividual differences between participants due to their personality, physiology, habits, and contexts. For sure we have seen interesting age and sex differences (the latter should perhaps be included more explicitly in future studies: although they are rarely targeted a priori, such differences were found in multiple exploratory analyses (ESR02, ESR03, ESR09). Important control measurements in the field include the objective and continuous logging of the very conditions we wanted to manipulate and hence perhaps take for granted: the actual light output of dynamic or automatic (intelligent) light systems, the behaviour (man-induced or automatic) of blinds, the weather conditions outside (ESR13, ESR14, ESR15). There is also growing awareness of the need to account for spatial or physical behaviour, and time of day (ESR13). But there are perhaps also downsides to the growing inclusion of measurements. For one, one should consider the participant burden that increases with every questionnaire item, sensor, or measurement instance we add. This is especially relevant when working with vulnerable populations such as patients, or those who cannot really give informed consent (e.g. children, animals) (ESR01, ESR02, ESR04, ESR06, ESR08, ESR14), but is, of course also relevant for healthy and cognitively competent participants. The same applies in the lab where we may perhaps not only raise participant burden but also bias our findings towards studies on humans under conditions of extreme boredom or distress after endless testing, needling, and fixed body or head positions.

A last aspect that surfaced during reflections on study design was the wealth of - potentially private and sensitive - insights that may be derived from the data we collect during studies. In particular if one considers the information included in longitudinal and sometimes even combined data on for instance full spectrum light exposure and actigraphy, we may well be able to reconstruct the life of our participants in great detail. Naturally, studies in LIGHTCAP all went through thorough ethical reviewing and our researchers tried their best to safeguard participants' privacy, but as our measurement devices are becoming more sensitive, reliable and robust, and as our data analysis tools are becoming more advanced, we may also need to establish more stringent rules on what to collect and keep, and which hypotheses and patterns to explore, or not.

3.1.3 Selecting the "best" method?

Across the studies, there was a large interest in the reaction time and accuracy tasks. Mostly PVT, but also ANT, Go/No-go, Oddball. These were all employed as measures of alertness even though they are different in the exact aspects of cognition they assess. When selecting the task to measure in the experiment, it is important to consider what kind of real-life task it represents and its context. On a similar note, different durations of these tasks were employed, ranging from short 3-minute ones to as long as 20 minutes. There are also options of how to process and analyse the reaction time and accuracy data. Choice of explored metrics therefore varies across studies and this should be taken into account when interpreting the results.

Regarding the self-reports, KSS was generally used as the main measure of subjective sleepiness. But similarly, as with the reaction time tasks, multiple scales were used with every metric focusing on a slightly different aspect of sleepiness. These details might seem minor but should not be disregarded. Future studies should pay attention to, and offer detailed explanations for, selecting a specific metric to help interpretation of the results.

3.2 Light Stimulus-Response Interaction

3.2.1 The complexity of light and NIF

The study of the effects of light is complex because it depends very much on the precise objective and the measures taken. In addition, the non-imaging effects of light are not specific, as they cover a wide range of actions. One of the lessons learned is to specify what NIF means in a particular study (i.e., NIF on circadian physiology, NIF on sleep, NIF on brain activity, NIF on retinal density, NIF on alertness and cognition, NIF on visual comfort, NIF on motor behaviour, etc.). Additionally, it is often difficult to disentangle image-forming and NIF effects, especially because participants are typically not blind to the light manipulation.

3.2.2 Temporal, spatial and spectral characteristics of the light stimulus

A further level of complexity is added by the properties of the light itself, with its dynamic temporal, spatial and spectral pattern, which is rarely taken into account in laboratory studies as an important modulator of NIF effects. Thus, light has at least 3 dimensions. One lesson learned is that while we now know that melanopsin-containing ganglion cells play an important role in transmitting NIF effects to the brain and the rest of the body, the role of classical photoreceptors and their interaction with ipRGCs is still under investigation. In addition, little is known about the interaction of temporal and spectral changes during the light-dark cycle and its impact on animal and human behaviour in general.

Another lesson learned is that the temporal pattern of light in seconds (flickering light) and hours (circadian light-dark cycles) is of paramount importance. The timing and duration of light exposure is crucial and can even lead to opposite effects of NIF on circadian physiology and sleep. Depending on its timing, the “same” light can phase advance or phase delay circadian rhythms and thus have wake-promoting or somnogenic properties. A lesson learned from here is that markers of circadian phase to have information about an individual’s biological time may be crucial in studies investigating NIF effects on sleep, alertness, and cognition.

Moreover, we learned that the spatial pattern of light – or its directionality – also moderates the response to light. A similar light dose in terms of spectrum and intensity, can trigger a different magnitude of alerting effect, depending on the direction of its origin. This was especially apparent in the time period of natural drop of alertness in the early afternoon.

3.2.3 Prior light history

It is known that the history of light exposure influences non-visual responses measured at a certain point in time (e.g., melatonin suppression). In most of the laboratory studies in the LIGHTCAP

project, dark adaptation periods before the experiment were used to equalize prior light history between subjects. However, it is unclear how many hours or days of prior light exposure need to be taken into account to control for its moderating effects. In addition, effects found using dark adaptation as control may have low external validity as continuous dark periods before daytime light exposure are rarely found in real life. A more realistic way to control for prior light history would be to measure personal light exposure with wearable light sensors (light-dosimetry). Since personal light exposure patterns are highly complex signals, it is still unclear how to quantify prior history from the collected dosimetry data as a covariate in statistical analyses.

Furthermore, the process of light-dosimetry requires careful consideration in order to retrieve reliable and accurate results. One ESR in this project (ESR13) focused on methodological aspects of light-dosimetry and the quantification and analysis of the data acquired with this method. Based on an extensive review of previous literature, a large variability in dosimetry methods was identified. Important points that were identified are the light sensor (dosimeter) used for data collection, including its response characteristics, appropriate calibration of the dosimeter, its placement on the body, and the sampling epoch. Although no consensus has yet been achieved on any of these points, preliminary recommendations include the selection of a dosimeter model that allows for sufficiently spectrally-resolved measurements to estimate alpha-opic quantities, calibration using a wide variety of light sources to avoid light source specific calibration bias, positioning the dosimeter in the vertical plane preferably at eye-level or alternatively at the chest, and selecting a sampling epoch of 1 minute or less to ensure an adequate temporal resolution to capture temporal trends in the data.

Regarding quantification and analysis of personal light exposure data, a wide variety of metrics exist to characterize and capture different aspects of light exposure patterns. Despite the large body of work using different metrics, to date it is unclear which metrics are better suited to characterize personal light exposure patterns. Especially for controlling potential confounding effects of prior light history, to this date it is not known how personal light exposure should be quantified and research in this direction is lacking. To our knowledge, no study has been specifically designed to address this question, highlighting an important route for future research.

Although some of the laboratory studies in the LIGHTCAP project included light-dosimetry as a control for prior light history, none have included it in the analyses, partly due to the questions raised above.

3.2.4 Laboratory versus field studies

While laboratory studies using animal and human models are well suited to investigate the mechanisms of NIF at the molecular, receptor, electrophysiological and perceptual levels, the transfer of this knowledge to the design of field studies is not always easy, but of ecological relevance. One lesson learned is that it is necessary to distil laboratory studies down to the most relevant light metrics to be implemented in field studies. This is of paramount importance to improve subject compliance in epidemiological studies investigating the effects of NIF on general health, without compromising the quality of the lighting assessment. To this end, the development of small light-measuring wearables capable of measuring the optimal setting of lighting parameters

needs to be advanced, together with personalised tracking of activity and sleep-wake behaviour using minimally obtrusive measures to facilitate intensive longitudinal monitoring. In addition, applying similar study and analyse methods, and protocols for light studies would be an essential step forward since it allows us to combine studies and therefore conduct meta-analysis (ESR06, ESR13, and ESR15). This is especially relevant for field studies where the number of confounding variables is large while the number of participants is relatively low.

3.2.5 Light sources for future research

Due to the vital role of the light source in lighting research, it is important to point out the constraints imposed by the lighting equipment. For instance, in the study on the role of cone contribution to human physiology (ESR05), a display with more monochromatic primaries would provide higher light contrast for each targeted photoreceptor. Consequently, the impact of modulated light stimuli on melatonin suppression could be greater.

References

(Alphabetically, by first author)	ESR#
Aarts, M. P. J., Hartmeyer, S. L., Morsink, K., & Kort, H. S. (2021, November). Exploring light exposure of hospital nurses working rapidly rotating shifts in relation to sleepiness and sleep. In <i>Journal of Physics: Conference Series</i> (Vol. 2042, No. 1, p. 012111). IOP Publishing. (https://iop-science.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/2042/1/012111/pdf)	13
Alshdaifat A, Fotios S. Road lighting and road user alertness at nighttime: Testing the null findings of Gibbons and Bhagavathula. Proceedings of the 30th Session of the CIE. Ljubljana, Slovenia, September 15 – 23, 2023. Vol. 1, Part 1: 624-630. https://doi.org/10.25039/x50.2023.OP047	10
Alshdaifat A, Moadab NH, Fotios S. The impact of road lighting on road user alertness in the evening. Lighting Research and Technology. First published online 10 June 2023 as https://doi.org/10.1177/14771535231172687	10,11
Alshdaifat A, Moadab NH, Fotios S. Alert to the problem? Lighting Journal May 2023; 88(5): 6-8 https://issuu.com/theilp/docs/lighting_journal_-_may_23	10,11
Alshdaifat A, Fotios S. Visiting academic. Lighting Journal February 2024; 89(2): 50-52	10
Beckers E, I. Campbell, R. Sharifpour, I. Paparella, A. Berger, J.F. Balda Aizpurua, E. Koshmanova, N. Mortazavi, P. Talwar, S. Sherif, H.I.L. Jacobs & G. Vandewalle (2023). Impact of repeated short light exposures on sustained pupil responses in an fMRI environment. https://doi.org/10.1111/jsr.14085	03,04
Campbell I, R. Sharifpour & G. Vandewalle (2022). Light as a Modulator of Non-Image-Forming Brain Functions—Positive and Negative Impacts of Increasing Light Availability. <i>Clocks & Sleep</i> 2023, 5(1), 116-140; https://doi.org/10.3390/clockssleep5010012	04
Campbell I, E. Beckers, R. Sharifpour, A. Berger, I. Paparella, J.F. Balda Aizpurua, E. Koshmanova, S. Sherif & G. Vandewalle (2023). Impact of light on task-evoked pupil responses during cognitive tasks. https://doi.org/10.1111/jsr.14101	03,04
Danell, M. N., Hartmeyer, S. L., Peterson, L., Davis, R., Andersen, M., Rockcastle, S. (2021). The Impact of Light Distribution and Furniture Layout on Meeting Light Exposure Objectives in an Office – A Simulation Case Study.’ Building Simulation. Bruges, Belgium. Sept 1-3, 2021. [International, Scientific]. Abstract	13,14
Fazlali, F., Stefani, O., Spitschan, M., Cajochen, C. (2023). Cone-photoreceptor contribution to melatonin suppression and subjective sleepiness. SLTBR, Lausanne, Switzerland	05
Fazlali, F., Cajochen, C., Stefani, O., Spitschan, M. (2023) Protocol + Preliminary results: Cone photoreceptors contribution on human neuroendocrine physiology. Sleep, Cognition & Consciousness” Symposium and DK Winter School, Salzburg, Austria	05
Fazlali, F., Cajochen, C., Stefani, O., Spitschan, M., Yahya, F. (2022) Cone photoreceptors contribution on human neuroendocrine physiology, Science Day of the Research Platform Molecular and Cognitive Neurosciences 2022, Basel, Switzerland	05
Fazlali, F., Cajochen, C., Stefani, O., Spitschan, M.(2022) Protocol: Mechanisms of Cone Photoreceptors Contribution to Human Neuroendocrine Physiology, Universitäre Psychiatrische Kliniken (UPK) Forschungskonferenz 2022, Basel, Switzerland	05

Gecer, Elifnaz, Poster presentation at the ILI/ILIAD 2021 edition of ILI annual public outreach event.	07
Gkaintatzi-Masouti, M., van Duijnhoven, J., Aarts, M. P. J. (2021) 'Review of spectral lighting simulation tools for non-image-forming effects of light', <i>CISBAT 2021</i> , [International, Scientific], Poster, Abstract	15
Gkaintatzi-Masouti, M., Duijnhoven, J. van, & Aarts, M. (2022). To What Extent are Non-visual Effects of Light Implemented in Current Lighting Design Practice? Findings from an International Survey. <i>Lux Europa</i> , 339–347. Article	15
Gkaintatzi-Masouti, M., Pierson, C., Van Duijnhoven, J., Andersen, M., & Aarts, M. P. J. (2022). A simulation tool for building and lighting design considering ipRGC-influenced light responses. <i>E3S Web of Conferences</i> , 362, 01001. https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202236201001	15
Gkaintatzi-Masouti, M., van Duijnhoven, J., & Aarts, M. P. J. (2022). Simulations of non-image-forming effects of light in building design: A literature review. <i>Lighting Research and Technology</i> . https://doi.org/10.1177/14771535221142812	15
Gkaintatzi-Masouti, M., van Duijnhoven, J., Aarts, M. P. J., & Heynderickx, I. (2024). Including Dynamic Viewing Behavior in Determining Vertical Eye-Level Light: Does it Matter for Office Design? <i>LEUKOS</i> , 1–22. https://doi.org/10.1080/15502724.2024.2366469	15
Hafezparast Moadab N, Alshdaifat A, Fotios S. The influence of light on alertness when walking or driving in the evening. Proceedings of the 14th European Lighting Conference Lux Europa 2022, 20 – 22 September 2022, Prague, Czech Republic. 5-8.	10,11
Hartmeyer, S. L., Webler, F. S., & Andersen, M. Towards a framework for light-dosimetry studies: methodological considerations. CIE Conference September 2021, Malaysia [International, Scientific] Full text	13
Hartmeyer, S. L., Rudawski, F. R., Knoop, M., & Andersen, M. (2023). Exploring spatiotemporal dynamics in light-dosimetry. <i>Journal of Physics: Conference Series</i> , 2600(11), 112005. https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2600/11/112005	13
Hartmeyer, S. L., Baldursdottir, B., Valdimarsdottir, H., Gudjonsson, I., Agustsson, G., & Andersen, M. (2023). Insights into spectrally resolved light-dosimetry data. <i>Proceedings of the 30th Quadrennial Session of the CIE</i> . 30th Quadrennial Session of the CIE, Vienna, Austria. https://doi.org/10.25039/x50.2023	13
Hartmeyer, S.L., Rudawski, F.R., Knoop, M., & Andersen, M. (2022). Quantification of light exposure characteristics modulating non-visual responses with light-dosimetry [Conference presentation abstract]. <i>33rd Annual Meeting of the Society for Light Treatment and Biological Rhythms (SLTBR)</i> , 23–25 June 2022, Manchester, UK, <i>Clocks & Sleep</i> 4(3) 412-457. https://doi.org/10.3390/clockssleep4030035	13
Hartmeyer, S. L., Webler, F. S., & Andersen, M. (2022). Towards a framework for light-dosimetry studies: Methodological considerations. <i>Lighting Research & Technology</i> , 14771535221103258. https://doi.org/10.1177/14771535221103258	13
Hartmeyer, S., & Andersen, M. (2023). Towards a framework for light-dosimetry studies: Quantification metrics. <i>Lighting Research & Technology</i> , 0(0), 14771535231170500. https://doi.org/10.1177/14771535231170500	13
Hartmeyer, S. L., Baldursdottir, B., Valdimarsdottir, H., Gudjonsson, I., Agustsson, G., & Andersen, M. (2024). Identification of spectral distributions in light-dosimetry data: Methodology and application to an intervention field study. <i>Lighting Research & Technology</i> , 14771535241265905. https://doi.org/10.1177/14771535241265905	13

- Jedon R, Haans A, de Kort Y. Proposing a research framework for urban lighting: The alertness, arousal and anxiety triad. *Lighting Research & Technology*. Lighting Research & Technology. 2022; 55 (7-8), 658-668. [doi:10.1177/14771535221122139](https://doi.org/10.1177/14771535221122139) 09
- Jedon R, Antal Haans, Yvonne de Kort. Challenging current urban lighting policies: Case for a shift of focus to alertness. International Conference proceedings. Shaping light for health and wellbeing in cities, pp. 82-84, DOI10.6092/UNIBO/AMSACTA/6863 [International, Scientific] [Abstract](#) 09
- Jedon R, [Poster presentation at the ILI/ILIAD 2021 edition of ILI annual public outreach event.](#) 09
- Lazar, R., & Spitschan, M. (2021, March 21–24). [Dynamic Real-World Measurements of Light-Mediated Changes in Pupil Size](#). [Conference Paper & Presentation]. LICHT2021 [24. Gemeinschaftstagung = 24th Associations meeting]. Online. 06
- Lazar, R., & Spitschan, M. (2022). Measuring regulation of pupil size under real-world conditions. *2021 Annual Meeting of the Swiss Society for Sleep Research, Sleep Medicine, and Chronobiology (SSSSC)*, 4, 306–307. <https://doi.org/10.3390/clockssleep4020026> 06
- Lazar, R., & Spitschan, M. (2023, May 30). Real-world variation of pupil size during activities of daily living across the lifespan. *34th Annual Meeting of the Society for Light Treatment and Biological Rhythms, Lausanne, CH*, 110. 06
- Lazar, R. , & Spitschan, M. (2022). Regulierung der Pupillengröße unter alltäglichen Bedingungen: Eine Feldstudie im Altersquerschnitt. *11. Symposium Licht Und Gesundheit*, 10–11. <https://doi.org/10.21934/BAUA:BERICHT20220316> 06
- Lazar, R., Degen, J., Fiechter, A. S., Monticelli, A., & Spitschan, M. (2024). Regulation of pupil size in natural vision across the human lifespan. *Royal Society Open Science*, 11(6), 191613. 06
- Lazar, R. (2022). Light flash therapy in the wild. *Nature Reviews Psychology*, 1(8), 437. <https://rdcu.be/cQH7W> 06
- Moadab NH, Mao Y, Fotios S. Improving the detection of pedestrians after dark. Proceedings of the 30th Session of the CIE. Ljubljana, Slovenia, September 15 – 23, 2023. Vol. 1, Part 1: 82-89. DOI 10.25039/x50.2023.OP006 11
- Opperhuizen, A.-L., van Lier, I. M. J., Hartmeyer, S. L., Aarts, M. P. J., & le Noble, J. L. M. L. (2023). Effectiveness of blue light-emitting glasses for intensive care unit health care workers on night shifts during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Intensive Care Medicine*, 49(10), 1256–1258. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00134-023-07175-9> 13
- Paparella, I., Campbell, I., Sharifpour, R., Beckers, E., Berger, A., Aizpurua, J. F. B., ... & Vandewalle, G. (2023). Light modulates task-dependent thalamo-cortical connectivity during an auditory attentional task. *Communications Biology*, 6(1), 945. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-023-05337-5> 03,04
- Pierson, C., Gkaintatzi-Masouti, M., Aarts, M.P.J., Andersen, M. (2021) 'Validation of spectral simulation tools for the prediction of indoor electric light exposure', in *CIE 2021 Conference* September 2021, Malaysia [International, Scientific]. [Abstract](#) 15
- Sharifpour R, I. Campbell, E. Beckers, & G. Vandewalle (2022). Pitfalls in recording BOLD signal responses to light in small hypothalamic nuclei using Ultra-High-Field 7 Tesla MRI. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.221212311> 03
- Sharifpour R, F. Balda Aizpurua, I. Paparella, I. Campbell, E. Beckers, N. Mortazavi , E. Koshmanova, C.Philips, G. Vandewalle. Impacts of Short Wavelength Light on Cortical Excitability . Poster presentation at Organization for Human Brain Mapping (OHBM), June 2024, Seoul, South Korea. 03,04

- Sharifpour R, I. Campbell, I. Paparella, E. Beckers, F. Balda Aizpurua, N. Mortazavi, A. Berger, P. Talwar, E. Koshmanova, L. Lamalle, S. Sherif, C. Philips, G. Vandewalle. Modulatory Effects of Melanopic Irradiance on Executive Brain activity in late teenagers and young adults. Oral presentation at Society for Light Treatment and Biological Rhythms(SLTBR), May 2023, Lausanne, Switzerland. 03,04
- Sharifpour R, I. Paparella, I. Campbell, E. Beckers, F. Balda Aizpurua, N. Mortazavi, A. Berger, P. Talwar, E. Koshmanova, L. Lamalle, S. Sherif, C. Philips, G. Vandewalle. Non-visual Impacts of Light on Effective Connectivity associated with executive brain responses. Poster presentation at Organization for Human Brain Mapping (OHBM), July 2023, Montreal, Canada. 03,04
- Sharifpour R, I. Campbell, I. Paparella, E. Beckers, F. Balda Aizpurua, N. Mortazavi, A. Berger, P. Talwar, E. Koshmanova, L. Lamalle, S. Sherif, G. Vandewalle. Ultra High Field 7 Tesla fMRI potential in revealing hypothalamus responses to blue-enriched light exposure. Poster presented at The 26th Conference of the European Sleep Research Society (ESRS), September 2022, Athen, Greece. 03,04
- Sharifpour R, I. Campbell, I. Paparella, E. Beckers, F. Balda Aizpurua, N. Mortazavi, A. Berger, P. Talwar, E. Koshmanova, L. Lamalle, S. Sherif, G. Vandewalle. Impacts of Light on Effective Connectivity Among the Working Memory Regions. Oral presentation at Society for Light Treatment and Biological Rhythms(SLTBR), June 2022, Manchester, United Kingdom. 03,04
- Sharifpour R, I. Campbell, I. Paparella, E. Beckers, T. Malik, S. Sherif, G. Vandewalle. Potential non-visual impact of light in the hypothalamus revealed with Ultra High Field (7-Tesla) fMRI. Poster presented at NEUROCOG, November 2021, Louvain-La-Neuve, Belgium. [Abstract](#) 03
- Sharifpour, R., Campbell, I., Paparella, I., Beckers, E., Aizpurua, F.B., Mortazavi, N., Berger, A., Talwar, P., Koshmanova, E. Lamalle, L., Sherif, S., Philips, C., Vandewalle, G. (2023). Modulatory Effects of Melanopic Irradiance on Executive Brain activity in late teenagers and young adults. Oral presentation at Society for Light Treatment and Biological Rhythms(SLTBR), May 2023, Lausanne, Switzerland. 03,04
- Sharifpour, R., Campbell, I., Paparella, I., Beckers, E., Aizpurua, F.B., Mortazavi, N., Berger, A., Talwar, P., Koshmanova, E. Lamalle, L., Sherif, S., Philips, C., Vandewalle, G. (2023). Non-visual Impacts of Light on Effective Connectivity associated to executive brain responses. Poster presentation at Organization for Human Brain Mapping (OHBM), July 2023, Montreal, Canada. 03,04
- Sharifpour, R., Campbell, I., Paparella, I., Beckers, E., Aizpurua, F.B., Mortazavi, N., Berger, A., Talwar, P., Koshmanova, E. Lamalle, L., Sherif, S., Philips, C., Vandewalle, G. (2022). Ultra High Field 7 Tesla fMRI potential in revealing hypothalamus responses to blue-enriched light exposure. Poster presented at The 26th Conference of the European Sleep Research Society (ESRS), September 2022, Athen, Greece. 03,04
- Sharifpour, R., Campbell, I., Paparella, I., Beckers, E., Aizpurua, F.B., Mortazavi, N., Berger, A., Talwar, P., Koshmanova, E. Lamalle, L., Sherif, S., Philips, C., Vandewalle, G. (2022) Modulatory effect of blue light on between regional connectivity: an Ultra High Field 7 Tesla fMRI ed study. Oral presentation at Society for Light Treatment and Biological Rhythms(SLTBR), June 2022, Manchester, United Kingdom. 03,04
- Siraji, M. A., **Lazar, R.**, van Duijnhoven, J., Schlangen, L. J., Haque, S., Kalavally, V., Vetter, C., Glickman, G., Smolders, K. C., & Spitschan, M. (2022). LEBA – a novel self-report instrument to capture light exposure-related behaviours. *CIE Australia Lighting Research Conference 2022, Online*, 1 06
- Siraji, M. A., **Lazar, R. R.**, van Duijnhoven, J., Schlangen, L. J., Haque, S., Kalavally, V., ... & Spitschan, M. (2023). An inventory of human light exposure behaviour. *Scientific reports*, 13(1), 22151. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-48241-y> 06

- Stampfli, J. R., Schrader, B., di Battista, C., Häfliger, R., Schälli, O., Wichmann, G., Zumbühl, C., Blattner, P., Cajochen, C., **Lazar, R.**, & Spitschan, M. (2023). The Light-Dosimeter: A new device to help advance research on the non-visual responses to light. *Lighting Research & Technology*, 14771535221147140. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14771535221147140> 06
- Stampfli, J.R., Schrader, B., di Battista, C., Häfliger, R., Schälli, O., Wichmann, G., Zumbühl, C., Blattner, P., Cajochen, C., Lazar, R. Spitschan, M. (2021) The Light–Dosimeter – [A New Device to Help Advance Research on the Non-Visual Responses to Light. CIE Conference September 2021, Malaysia \[International, Scientific\]](#). 06
- Verhoef, Vaida, [Poster presentation at the ILI/ILIAD 2021 edition of ILI annual public outreach event.](#) 08
- Verhoef, V.T. R., Smolders, K.C.H.J., Rimmelswaal, L., Peeters, G., Overeem, S., & de Kort, Y. A. W. (2024). Match and Mismatch between Lived Experiences of Daytime Sleepiness and Diagnostic Instruments: A Qualitative Study amongst Patients with Sleep Disorders. *Clocks & Sleep*, 6, 24-39. [10.3390/clockssleep6010003](https://doi.org/10.3390/clockssleep6010003) 08